

CAP Objectives and challenges

- Agroforestry excellently aligns with the CAP productive sustainability goals linked to fair income, competitiveness and food value chain associated with the farm to fork, bioeconomy and circular economy EU strategies and the efficiency, recycling and circular and solidarity economy FAO agroecology elements.
- Agroforestry excellently aligns with the CAP environmental sustainability goals related to climate change, environmental care and landscapes linked to the climate change, environmental care and landscape linked to the climate change, forest and biodiversity EU strategies associated with the resilience and diversity FAO agroecology elements
- Agroforestry excellently aligns with the CAP social sustainability goals associated with the generational renewal, rural areas and food and health linked to the EU forest and rural areas strategy and related to the human and social values, culture and food traditions of the FAO agroecology elements.

Agroforestry in the CAP

Agroforestry understood as the integration of woody perennials with an agriculture product (Annex I of the CAP) produced as part of the understory is linked to the CAP main objectives structured as productive (fair income, competitiveness and food value chain) linked to the bioeconomy, circular economy and farm EU strategies, environmental (climate change, environmental care and landscape) associated with the biodiversity and forest strategy and social (rural areas, food and health and generation renewal) related to the EU strategy for rural revival sustainability goals, having as a horizontal goal linked to the knowledge an innovation. Moreover, the EU goals are linked to the main FAO agroecology elements.

FIGURE 1. Modified from 10 CAP Objectives (European Commission), including relations to other EU Strategies, FAO agroecology elements and CAP objectives

Agroforestry and the sustainability productive goals

Agroforestry should be promoted as a tool able linked to sustainability as silvopasture, agrisilviculture and agrosilvopasture practices are usually linked to short value chains associated with fair income, moreover it increases competitiveness in the sense that increases resilience therefore promoting competitiveness at farm level. Agroforestry and the sustainability productive goals. Moreover, agroforestry is linked to the bioeconomy and circular economy strategies. The bioeconomy is produced by the increase of the biomass production per unit on land under agroforestry compared with treeless systems, mainly if the woody perennial is a processed product. The diversified value chains is able to increase both the recycling and the circular economy.

Agroforestry and the sustainability environmental goals

Agroforestry is able to mitigate climate change thanks to the capacity it has to sequester carbon due to the higher photosynthetic activity agroforestry has compared with tree less systems that increases the biomass production by around 25%. Moreover, agroforestry also contributes to increase resilience against extreme events such as droughts, frosts or forest fires.

Agroforestry is also able to enhance environmental care associated with biodiversity water and soil health. Biodiversity is enhanced because the presence of a woody perennial increases the soil heterogeneity and therefore the number of species able to grow in different conditions per unit of land. The dehesa is an excellent example of this biodiversity. Running and stored water quality is promoted due to the capacity that roots have to uptake nutrients when they are not used by the understorey, therefore mostly reducing nitrate leaching to waters. Soil health is enhanced by the soil capitalization linked to the higher organic matter inputs of agroforestry compared with treeless systems. Moreover, landscape beauty is benefited thanks to the increase of biodiversity at landscape level relying on the traditional land management of agroforestry. From an environmental perspective, agroforestry is associated with the FAO elements of enhanced biodiversity and resilience.

Agroforestry and the sustainability social goals

Agroforestry is able to enhance sustainability social goals linked to generation renewal as it optimizes the use of the resources matching the existing resources to already known traditional farming systems based on the use of woody perennials and providing extra incomes from diversified value chains that allows to increase profitability and makes more attractive rural areas for generational renewal needed in the current negative demographic context. Rural areas are enhanced due to the dynamization caused by agroforestry implementation contributing to the promotion of increasing extra income, beautiful landscapes that enhances agrotourism short and long-term experiences. Moreover, the fact that agroforestry is mostly based on the use of their own resources and more biodiversity together with the fact that promotes the use of autochthonous livestock breeds better adapted to the environment and the

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diversified value chains enhances promotes food and health and the better interconnectivity of rural and urban areas associated with the promotion of short value chains. From an agroecological perspective, agroforestry enhances culture and food traditions and human and social values.

MAIN CONCLUSION

- Agroforestry is able to fulfil the EU 10 CAP objectives linked to the EU green deal and responsible governance, based on the productive, environmental and social CAP goals.
- Agroforestry fosters productivity thanks to ecointensification processes linked to the optimization of the use of the external and internal resources
- Agroforestry enhances environment thanks to the capacity of sequesters more carbon and the optimization of the use of internal resources more aligned with nature based solutions
- Agroforestry promotes social values as it is based in traditional knowledge linked to cultural values.

FIGURE 2. A group of Children playing the AF4EU MEMO-GAME learning concepts about sustainability and agroforestry systems, during Galician G-NIGHT in Lugo, Spain. Couso, A.

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